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Speech-dependent data augmentation for own voice reconstruction with hearable microphones in noisy environments

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Abstract

Hearable devices, equipped with one or more microphones, can be used to capture the user's own voice in noisy environments. In such environments, an own voice reconstruction (OVR) system is needed to enhance the quality and intelligibility of the recorded own voice. In this work, we aim to estimate clean broadband speech from a microphone at the outer face of the hearable and an in-ear microphone, which captures the own voice at a higher signal-to-noise ratio than the outer microphone, but with a limited bandwidth and additive body-produced noise. Training a supervised deep learning-based OVR system requires a substantial amount of own voice signals as training data. Such training data can be collected by recording many utterances from different talkers wearing the hearable, which is costly, or generated by augmenting existing clean speech datasets. In this paper, we investigate several data augmentation techniques to simulate a large amount of in-ear own voice signals from a limited amount of recorded own voice signals. More specifically, we consider different models for the own voice transfer characteristics between the outer microphone and the in-ear microphone, ranging from a fixed talker-averaged relative transfer function to a phoneme-dependent individual model. We investigate the influence of the amount of recorded own voice signals on the performance of an OVR system based on the FT-JNF architecture, either by directly using the recorded signals for training or by using the recorded signals to generate augmented data for training (with and without fine-tuning with recorded signals). Experimental results show that training using the proposed speech-dependent individual data augmentation technique and additional fine-tuning with recorded signals yields the best performance in terms of objective metrics, even when only few recorded own voice signals are available.

Keywords Data augmentation, Hearables, Multi-microphone speech enhancement, Own voice reconstruction, Voice pickup, Individual models

1 Introduction

Speech communication is often impaired in noisy environments, such as busy traffic areas or industrial manufacturing sites. In such environments, hearable devices

with integrated microphones can be used to improve communication, e.g., by capturing and transmitting the user's own voice to a mobile phone or another hearable [1, 2]. In addition to applications in person-to-person communication, own voice pickup can also improve automatic speech recognition [3], enabling more robust control of production machines [4], hearing aids [5], and using voice assistants [6]. In this paper, we consider a hearable equipped with two microphones: a microphone at the outer face (outer microphone) and a microphone inside the partly occluded ear canal (in-ear microphone). Since the hearable occluding the ear canal attenuates

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environmental noise, the in-ear microphone may be particularly beneficial, since it captures the user's own voice at a higher signal-to-noise ratio than the outer microphone. However, compared to own voice recorded at the outer microphone, own voice recorded at the in-ear microphone is subject to amplification at low frequencies (below approximately 1 kHz) and strong attenuation at higher frequencies (above approximately 2 kHz), resulting in a limited bandwidth and poor signal quality [7]. In addition, the in-ear microphone also records body-produced noise, such as respiratory and heart sounds [8]. It has been shown that the ratio between the airborne and body-conducted components of own voice recorded at an in-ear microphone depends on the phonetic content [9, 10] (e.g., due to mouth movements or place of excitation changes), and the individual user [11, 12]. In this paper, the relationship between own voice recorded at the outer microphone and the in-ear microphone is referred to as own voice transfer characteristics. Several models of own voice transfer characteristics have been presented in the literature. In [13–15] the own voice transfer characteristics are modeled using a time-invariant relative transfer function, whereas in [16] the own voice transfer characteristics are modeled using a relative transfer function for each phoneme, leading to a (time-varying) speech-dependent model.

Since neither the quality of the outer microphone nor the in-ear microphone is sufficient, several own voice reconstruction (OVR) algorithms have been proposed that aim at estimating clean broadband speech from the (noisy) outer microphone signal and/or the (band-limited) in-ear microphone signal. Classical signal processing approaches for reconstructing own voice using body-conduction microphones¹ are based on, e.g., equalization filter design [17], linear prediction analysis and synthesis [18], or statistical modeling [19]. In [20], bandwidth extension based on classical signal processing has been applied to in-ear own voice signals for reconstructing high-frequency content. However, the quality of own voice processed by classical approaches is typically limited since body-conduction of own voice is difficult to account for. Many recent OVR approaches using body-conduction microphones or in-ear microphones are based on deep learning [13, 21–31]. Most deep learning-based approaches are trained using large amounts of device-specific recorded own voice signals, such as the ESMB corpus [26] or the VibraVox corpus [32]. However, since recording a large amount of own voice

signals requires a lot of recording effort, it has also been proposed to perform data augmentation by simulating own voice signals to enable training with less recording effort [13–15, 33, 34]. Although data augmentation by simulating microphone signals is quite common, e.g., to simulate different room characteristics [35–37], it should be realized that simulating bone conduction or in-ear own voice microphone signals is more challenging, since the own voice transfer characteristics are typically speech-dependent, device-specific and individual. In [33], it was proposed to simulate bone-conduction microphone own voice signals using a deep neural network (DNN) in an adversarial training paradigm. While the presented semi-supervised scheme enabled to reduce the amount of recorded own voice signals by half without sacrificing performance compared to supervised training with the full dataset, the performance deteriorated when the amount of recorded signals was reduced further. In [13], a speech-independent data augmentation technique was proposed to train an OVR system by simulating in-ear own voice signals based on relative transfer functions (RTFs) between an outer microphone and an in-ear microphone. The performance increased by introducing variance to the simulated own voice signals by considering RTFs estimated from different segments and different talkers. Additionally, the performance notably improved by fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals after training with simulated own voice signals. In [15], a similar data augmentation technique as in [13] was used to simulate bone-conduction signals. Instead of using RTFs from different segments and talkers, in [14] it was proposed to introduce additional variance to the simulated own voice signals by adding random values to the magnitude of the RTF estimated from a single talker during training, resulting in a performance increase. In [34], it was proposed to perform talker-specific fine-tuning after training with simulated data, obtained with speech-independent data augmentation techniques similar to [13–15]. A considerable performance gain from fine-tuning was observed even when only few recorded own voice signals were available.

While previous studies in [13–15, 34] have investigated the use of speech-independent data augmentation techniques, in this paper we investigate speech-dependent data augmentation techniques to train an OVR system using simulated in-ear own voice signals. The proposed data augmentation techniques (see Fig. 1) use a small amount of own voice signals recorded with several talkers wearing a hearable device [38] to first estimate models of own voice transfer characteristics [16]. These models can then be used to simulate a large amount of in-ear own voice signals from a dataset of clean speech signals to train an OVR system. In this paper, we will

¹ Most approaches proposed and validated for body-conduction microphones can also be applied to in-ear microphones, as considered in this paper.

Fig. 1 Data augmentation with own voice transfer characteristic models, which are estimated from recorded outer and in-ear microphone signals. During data augmentation, in-ear own voice signals are simulated from a speech dataset using the estimated own voice transfer characteristic models

compare data augmentation using (individual or talker-averaged) speech-dependent models with speech-independent models. We will consider three different training procedures: training with a small amount of recorded signals, training with a large amount of simulated signals, and fine-tuning with recorded signals after training with simulated signals. For the three considered training procedures, we investigate the influence of the amount of recorded own voice signals, both in terms of number of talkers as well as number of utterances per talker on the OVR performance. Experiments are carried out for an OVR system based on the joint spatial and tempo-spectral non-linear filter (FT-JNF) architecture [39], using both the outer and in-ear microphone signal as input to estimate clean broadband speech. Results show that the proposed speech-dependent data augmentation results in higher OVR performance than speech-independent data augmentation. Speech-dependent individual data augmentation outperforms training using only the recorded own voice signals, while performance can still be considerably improved by additional fine-tuning. In addition, results show that the number of recorded utterances per talker has a smaller influence on the OVR performance than the number of recorded talkers. Moreover, the results demonstrate that the proposed speech-dependent individual data augmentation is still highly effective even when only a limited amount of recorded own voice signals is available.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the signal model is introduced and the considered speech-independent and speech-dependent own voice transfer characteristic models are presented. Based on these models, in Section 3 several data augmentation techniques are proposed to simulate in-ear own voice

signals to train an OVR system. In Section 4, the experimental evaluation setup for investigating the proposed data augmentation techniques and training procedures is described. In Section 5, the experimental results are presented and discussed.

2 Own voice transfer characteristic models

After introducing the signal model in Section 2.1, speech-independent and speech-dependent own voice transfer characteristic models are presented in Section 2.2.

2.1 Signal model

Consider a hearable device equipped with an outer microphone and an in-ear microphone, as depicted in Fig. 2. The microphone signals are denoted by subscripts o for the outer microphone and i for the in-ear

Fig. 2 Block diagram of a multi-microphone OVR system using an outer and an in-ear microphone of a hearable device. The own voice transfer characteristics of talker a between the outer and in-ear microphone are represented by T^a

microphone, respectively. We assume that the hearable is worn by a person (referred to as talker) in a noisy environment. The time-domain signals $s_o^a[n]$ and $s_i^a[n]$ denote the own voice of talker a at the outer microphone and the in-ear microphone, respectively, where n denotes the discrete-time index. The outer microphone signal $y_o^a[n]$ consists of the own voice component $s_o^a[n]$ and the environmental noise component $v_o^a[n]$ (including sensor noise), i.e.,

$$y_o^a[n] = s_o^a[n] + v_o^a[n]. \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the in-ear microphone signal $y_i^a[n]$ consists of the own voice component $s_i^a[n]$, the environmental noise component $v_i^a[n]$ (including sensor noise), and body-produced noise $u_i^a[n]$ (e.g., respiratory and heart sounds), i.e.,

$$y_i^a[n] = s_i^a[n] + v_i^a[n] + u_i^a[n]. \quad (2)$$

In practice, the recorded own voice signal at the in-ear microphone also contains body-produced noise. The relationship between the own voice components of talker a at the outer microphone and the in-ear microphone is referred to as the own voice transfer characteristics $T^a\{\cdot\}$, i.e.,

$$s_i^a[n] = T^a\{s_o^a[n]\}. \quad (3)$$

2.2 Own voice transfer characteristic models

In [13–16], several models for the own voice transfer characteristics $T^a\{\cdot\}$ have been proposed. The transfer characteristics are either modeled as a time-invariant or a time-varying linear system, either for each individual talker or averaged over all talkers. In the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) domain, the time-varying system is approximated² as

$$S_i^a(k, l) = H^a(k, l) \cdot S_o^a(k, l), \quad (4)$$

where k denotes the frequency bin index, l denotes the time frame index and $H^a(k, l)$ denotes the time-varying RTF of talker a between the outer microphone and the in-ear microphone. Assuming that own voice recordings of multiple talkers in a noiseless environment are available and sensor noise can be neglected compared to the own voice components in both microphone signals, i.e., $v_o^a[n] \approx 0$ and $v_i^a[n] \approx 0$, the following speech-independent and speech-dependent models have been proposed:

1. *Speech-independent models*: if the own voice transfer characteristics are assumed to be independent of the phonetic content, the transfer characteristics of talker a can be modeled as a time-invariant RTF $H^a(k)$. Considering all active STFT frames of the recorded microphone signals of talker a , the least-squares RTF estimate [40] is given by

$$\hat{H}^a(k) = \frac{\sum_l Y_i^a(k, l) \cdot Y_o^{a,*}(k, l)}{\sum_l |Y_o^a(k, l)|^2}, \quad (5)$$

where $*$ denotes complex conjugation and it is assumed that the own voice component at the outer microphone and the body-produced noise at the in-ear microphone are independent. Since this speech-independent model is based only on recorded microphone signals of talker a , it is an individual model. A speech-independent talker-averaged model can be obtained by performing RTF estimation using all STFT frames of the recorded microphone signals of all talkers, i.e.,

$$\hat{H}^{\text{avg}}(k) = \frac{\sum_a \sum_l Y_i^a(k, l) \cdot Y_o^{a,*}(k, l)}{\sum_a \sum_l |Y_o^a(k, l)|^2}. \quad (6)$$

2. *Speech-dependent models*: since the own voice transfer characteristics in general depend on the phonetic content, it has been proposed in [16] to model the transfer characteristics using a time-varying model, assuming that the transfer characteristics for each phoneme can be modeled as a time-invariant RTE. First, the frame-wise phoneme sequence $p_o^a(l) \in \{1, \dots, P\}$, with P possible phoneme classes, is obtained from the (noiseless) outer microphone signal $y_o^a[n]$ using a phoneme recognition system. The RTF for phoneme p' is then estimated from all STFT frames in which this phoneme is present as

$$\hat{H}_{p'}^a(k) = \frac{\sum_{p_o^a(l)=p'} Y_i^a(k, l) \cdot Y_o^{a,*}(k, l)}{\sum_{p_o^a(l)=p'} |Y_o^a(k, l)|^2}, \quad p' = 1, \dots, P. \quad (7)$$

Since this model is based only on recorded microphone signals of talker a , it is a speech-dependent individual model. A speech-dependent talker-averaged model can be obtained by performing RTF estimation using all STFT frames of the recorded microphone signals of all talkers in which phoneme p' is present, i.e.,

$$\hat{H}_{p'}^{\text{avg}}(k) = \frac{\sum_a \sum_{p_o^a(l)=p'} Y_i^a(k, l) \cdot Y_o^{a,*}(k, l)}{\sum_a \sum_{p_o^a(l)=p'} |Y_o^a(k, l)|^2}, \quad p' = 1, \dots, P. \quad (8)$$

Although this speech-dependent talker-averaged model does not account for individual differences, it has been shown in [16] that on average it is able to estimate in-ear own voice signals of different talkers

² This approximation is only time-varying between STFT frames and not within a single STFT frame. Circular convolution effects are also neglected in this approximation, but can be reduced by appropriate windowing.

(i.e., under talker mismatch) better than speech-dependent individual models.

3 Data augmentation techniques using own voice transfer characteristic models

In order to train a deep learning-based OVR system aiming at estimating clean broadband speech from both the (noisy) outer microphone signal and the (band-limited) in-ear microphone signal, a large amount of own voice signals is required. Instead of recording a large amount of own voice signals, in this section we propose several data augmentation techniques using the own voice transfer characteristic models presented in Section 2.2. These models can be used to simulate in-ear own voice signals and can be estimated from a relatively small amount of recorded own voice signals (see Fig. 1). In addition to speech-independent data augmentation, we propose two phoneme-dependent data augmentation techniques to simulate in-ear own voice signals, either using matching phoneme sequences or random phoneme sequences. While several speech-independent data augmentation techniques have been proposed in the literature [13–15], our goal is not to benchmark all of them. Instead, we have considered a representative speech-independent baseline that conceptually aligns with [13], where speech-independent RTFs are used to generate training data. An overview of the proposed data augmentation techniques is presented in Table 1, also indicating the time-variance and the number of used RTFs.

For all data augmentation techniques, the in-ear own voice signals are simulated from large datasets of clean speech signals (e.g., LibriSpeech [41], Common Voice [42]) instead of from recorded outer microphone own voice signals. This has the advantage that simulating a large amount of in-ear own voice signals is easily feasible, even though no individual transfer characteristic models are available for the talkers in these datasets. To obtain an augmented in-ear own voice signal $\hat{s}_i[n]$, a speech signal $s[n]$ from the dataset is selected as the outer microphone own voice signal. In the STFT domain, the augmented in-ear own voice signal $\hat{S}_i(k, l)$ is generated based on (4), i.e.,

$$\hat{S}_i(k, l) = \hat{H}(k, l) \cdot S(k, l), \quad (9)$$

where depending on the data augmentation technique, different RTF estimates $\hat{H}(k, l)$ are used (see below). Finally, the augmented in-ear own voice signal $\hat{s}_i[n]$ is computed by transforming $\hat{S}_i(k, l)$ back to the time domain using a weighted overlap-add (WOLA) scheme. We will now discuss the considered data augmentation techniques in more detail:

1. *Speech-independent augmentation*: when performing data augmentation using speech-independent individual models, the augmented in-ear own voice signals are generated using time-invariant RTFs as

$$\hat{S}_i(k, l) = \hat{H}^a(k) \cdot S(k, l). \quad (10)$$

For each speech signal from the dataset, the RTF estimate $\hat{H}^a(k)$ in (5) of a random talker a is chosen (for the entire signal) from all available talkers, similarly as in [13]. When performing data augmentation using the speech-independent talker-averaged model, the RTF estimate $\hat{H}^{\text{avg}}(k)$ in (6) is used instead of $\hat{H}^a(k)$ in (10), i.e., the same time-invariant RTF is used for all augmented in-ear own voice signals.

2. *Speech-dependent augmentation*: when performing data augmentation using speech-dependent individual models, the frame-wise phoneme sequence $p(l)$ is first determined for the speech signal $s[n]$ and then used to select the matching phoneme-specific RTF estimate $\hat{H}_{p(l)}^a(k)$ in (7) for each STFT frame. Similarly as for speech-independent individual augmentation, a random talker a is chosen for the entire signal. To prevent discontinuities during phoneme transitions, recursive smoothing is applied to the RTF estimates, i.e.,

$$\tilde{H}_{p(l)}^a(k) = \alpha \cdot \tilde{H}_{p(l-1)}^a(k) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \hat{H}_{p(l)}^a(k), \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{H}_{p(l)}^a(k)$ denotes the smoothed RTF of talker a for frame l , and α denotes the (time- and frequency-independent) smoothing constant. Using the

Table 1 Overview of the proposed augmentation techniques

Augmentation technique		Time-variance	Number of RTFs
Speech-independent	Individual	Time-invariant	Number of talkers
	Talker-averaged	Time-invariant	1
Speech-dependent	Individual	Phoneme-dependent	$P \times$ Number of talkers
	Talker-averaged	Phoneme-dependent	P
Random phoneme	Individual	Random	$P \times$ Number of talkers

Table 2 Overview of the speech and noise datasets used in the experimental evaluation

Use of dataset	Speech (own voice)	Noise
Estimation of transfer characteristic models	Recorded own voice signals (training/validation set, max. 12/2 talkers, max. 306 utterances, max. 6/1 h) ¹	–
Training/validation (recorded signals)	Recorded own voice signals (training/validation set, max. 12/2 talkers, max. 306 utterances, max. 6/1 h) ¹	Individually spatialized noise (120.7/20.1 h) ²
Training/validation (augmented signals)	Augmented own voice signals (115.7 h)	Individually spatialized noise (120.7/20.1 h) ²
Fine-tuning	Recorded own voice signals (training/validation set, max. 12/2 talkers, max. 306 utterances, max. 6/1 h) ¹	Individually spatialized noise (120.7/20.1 h) ²
Evaluation	Recorded own voice signals (test set, 4 talkers, 306 utterances, max. 2 h)	Individually spatialized noise (40.2 h)

The speech and the noise datasets are disjoint between training/validation/fine-tuning and evaluation. All dataset splits marked by ¹ and all splits marked by ² are identical, respectively

smoothed RTFs, the augmented in-ear own voice signals are generated as

$$\hat{S}_i(k, l) = \tilde{H}_{p(l)}^a(k) \cdot S_o(k, l). \quad (12)$$

When performing data augmentation using the speech-dependent talker-averaged model, the talker-averaged phoneme-specific RTFs $\hat{H}_{p(l)}^{\text{avg}}(k)$ in (8) are used instead of $\hat{H}_{p(l)}^a(k)$ in (11). Compared to speech-independent augmentation, speech-dependent augmentation does not only introduce time-varying speech-dependent behavior, but also incorporates additional variance into the training dataset by using P times more phoneme-specific RTFs (see Table 1).

3. *Random phoneme individual augmentation*: to investigate the influence of speech-dependency and additional variance in the training dataset separately, we also consider an individual augmentation technique using random RTF selection instead of speech-dependent RTF selection, i.e., instead of obtaining the phoneme sequence $p(l)$ from $s[n]$, the phoneme sequence is randomly generated. This augmentation technique uses the same amount of RTFs as speech-dependent individual augmentation, but applies the RTFs of random phonemes instead of matching phonemes³.

In the experimental evaluation (see Sections 4 and 5), we will compare the performance of the presented data augmentation techniques when training an OVR system using a large amount of simulated own voice signals. In addition, we will investigate the influence of the number of recorded talkers and recorded utterances per talker,

which are used to estimate the own voice transfer characteristic models required for data augmentation.

4 Experimental setup

This section describes the experimental setup used to evaluate the influence of the proposed data augmentation techniques on the performance of an OVR system. Section 4.1 provides details on the speech and noise datasets used for training and evaluation. Section 4.2 describes the DNN architecture of the OVR system. Section 4.3 describes the training procedures and the hyperparameters, and Section 4.4 discusses the experimental evaluation conditions and performance metrics.

4.1 Datasets

This section discusses the speech and noise datasets used for estimating the own voice transfer characteristic models and for training and evaluating the OVR system. The recordings and the experimental validation were conducted at a sampling frequency of 16 kHz. An overview of the datasets and their usage is presented in Table 2.

4.1.1 Recorded own voice signals

Own voice signals from 18 native German talkers (5 female, 13 male) were recorded (see [16] for details). The talkers were wearing the closed-vent variant of the Hearpiece [38], a prototype hearable device with an in-ear microphone and multiple outer microphones, of which the *Concha* microphone was chosen as the outer microphone in the experiments. Both microphones are Knowles SPH1642HT5H-1 MEMS microphones. For each talker, utterances of 306 phonetically balanced and representative German sentences were recorded, corresponding to approximately 25 to 30 min of own voice recordings per talker (approximately 9 h in total). Although own voice recordings were performed at both ears, only the recordings at the left ear were considered here. The recorded own voice signals were split

³ Although it would also be possible to consider random phoneme talker-averaged augmentation, this would incorporate less variance into the training dataset than random phoneme individual augmentation, such that we chose not to investigate it.

into disjoint training, validation and test sets of 12, 2, and 4 talkers, respectively. Training and validation sets were used for estimating transfer characteristic models for data augmentation and for training directly on the recorded signals. The test set was used exclusively for evaluating the OVR systems.

To estimate the own voice transfer characteristic models from the recorded own voice signals, we followed the procedure described in Section 2.2. RTFs were estimated using either all utterances available for each talker (individual) or all utterances available for all talkers (talker-averaged) in the training set. For the speech-dependent models, a proprietary in-house phoneme recognition system was used, which was trained with about 1000 h of German speech and distinguishes between $P = 62$ phoneme classes. The system is similar to the system used in [43] and uses Mel-Filterbank features as input to a temporal convolutional neural network architecture. The system provides phoneme labels with 30 ms temporal resolution, which are matched to STFT frames based on minimal temporal distance. Since the recorded in-ear own voice signals are band-limited, the RTFs were estimated at a sampling frequency of 5 kHz, by first downsampling the microphone signals. The RTFs were estimated in an STFT framework with a frame length of 25.6 ms (128 samples), 50 % overlap, and a square-root Hann analysis window. After simulation, the augmented in-ear own voice signals were upsampled to 16 kHz again. The same procedure is carried out separately for the validation set to estimate own voice transfer characteristic models used in validation.

4.1.2 Augmented own voice signals

The estimated own voice transfer characteristic models were used for data augmentation to obtain simulated in-ear own voice signals (see Fig. 1). Since own voice data augmentation is only carried out for training and validation, RTFs from the previous subsection are estimated using only the training and validation subsets, amounting to approx. 6/1 h, respectively (see Table 2). For the outer microphone signals, clean speech signals from the Common Voice dataset [42] were used (German part, v11.0, only *validated* subset). While the Common Voice dataset consists of 1157 h of speech signals, only 10% of this dataset (corresponding to 115.7 h) was used to construct the augmented own voice dataset, since preliminary experiments suggest that this amount is sufficient for training an OVR system. Several data augmentation techniques were considered (see Section 3), namely speech-independent augmentation (individual and talker-averaged), speech-dependent augmentation (individual and talker-averaged) and random phoneme augmentation (individual). The models were applied at a sampling frequency

of 5 kHz, by downsampling the clean speech signals, and using the same STFT framework as for model estimation. For speech-dependent augmentation, the same phoneme recognition system as for model estimation was used to determine the frame-wise phoneme sequence from the clean speech signals. Smoothing of the RTFs in (11) was carried out with $\alpha = 0.8$ for both speech-dependent and random phoneme augmentation. If the speech-dependent and random phoneme augmentation techniques encountered a phoneme during simulation for which no RTF estimate is available, a fallback RTF averaged over all available phoneme RTF estimates was used. This may happen when only few recorded utterances are available to estimate the own voice transfer characteristics (as in Section 5.3). The augmented in-ear own voice signals in the STFT domain were transformed back to the time domain using a WOLA scheme with a square-root Hann synthesis window and were upsampled to 16 kHz. The same procedure is carried out separately with the own voice transfer characteristic models for the validation set to obtain simulated in-ear own voice signals for validation.

4.1.3 Environmental noise

The environmental noise used for training, validation, and testing is a spatialized version of the noise dataset from the fifth DNS challenge [44], consisting of approximately 181 h of environmental noise. Since it was shown in [28] that training an OVR system with individually spatialized noise signals generalizes well to recorded noise signals, individually measured device-specific transfer functions from different directions were used to generate the noise components in the outer and in-ear microphones for each talker. The transfer functions between 8 loudspeakers and both microphones were measured for all talkers using exponential sweeps. The loudspeakers were positioned at approximately 1.5 m distance from the talker in 45°-steps in the horizontal plane.

Half of the spatialized noise dataset consisted of point noise sources, while the other half consisted of pseudo-diffuse noise. To generate the point noise source signals, a random noise sample from the DNS dataset was filtered with the device-specific transfer functions corresponding to a random direction. To generate the pseudo-diffuse noise signals, time-shifted copies of a random noise sample from the DNS dataset were filtered with the transfer functions for the all directions, and then added. To account for body-produced noise, which is present in the recorded own voice signals, white noise was added to the spatialized in-ear signal with a random level uniformly distributed in the range of $[-\infty, -60]$ dB relative to the in-ear environmental noise signal.

Fig. 3 Architecture of the OVR system

The noise dataset was split into equal parts (approximately 10.1h per talker), so that different noise types are spatialized with individually measured impulse responses for each talker. This way, different noise types are included in training and validation than in evaluation.

4.2 Own voice reconstruction system

Figure 3 depicts the considered OVR system, which is based on the FT-JNF DNN architecture [39]. The noisy microphone signals $y_o[n]$ and $y_i[n]$ are transformed into the STFT domain with a frame length of 32 ms (512 samples), 50% overlap and a square-root Hann analysis window. The (broadband) own voice component in the outer microphone signal is then estimated by applying complex-valued masks to the outer and in-ear microphone signals, i.e.,

$$\hat{S}_o(k, l) = M_o(k, l) \cdot Y_o(k, l) + M_i(k, l) \cdot Y_i(k, l), \quad (13)$$

where $M_o(k, l)$ and $M_i(k, l)$ denote the mask for the outer and in-ear microphone, respectively. Even though the in-ear microphone signal only contains band-limited own voice, it was shown in [28] that combining both microphone signals leads to a higher performance than only applying a mask to the outer microphone signal due to a better noise reduction in the lower frequencies. The inputs to the DNN are the real and imaginary parts of the complex-valued STFT coefficients $Y_o(k, l)$ and $Y_i(k, l)$. The DNN architecture consists of a uni-directional long short-term memory (LSTM) layer with 512 hidden units operating along the frequency dimension (F-LSTM), followed by a uni-directional LSTM layer with 128 hidden units operating along the time dimension (T-LSTM). This is followed by a dense layer combining the 128 outputs of the second LSTM layer to 4 outputs, followed by a tanh activation. The outputs of the DNN are the real and imaginary parts of the complex-valued masks $M_o(k, l)$ and $M_i(k, l)$. Overall, the OVR system consists of approximately 1.39 million parameters, requires about 22.45 billion multiply-accumulate operations (MACs) per second⁴. Table 3 provides an overview of the complexity

of the DNN required for each individual layer. The estimated STFT coefficient in (13) is transformed back to the time-domain signal $\hat{s}_o[n]$ using a WOLA scheme with a square-root Hann synthesis window.

4.3 Training procedures

The OVR system was trained on mixtures of recorded or augmented own voice signals and spatialized environmental noise signals, truncated to a signal length of 3 s. The own voice and noise components $S_o(k, l)$ and $V_o(k, l)$ in the outer microphone signal were added as

$$Y_o(k, l) = S_o(k, l) + q \cdot V_o(k, l), \quad (14)$$

where the scaling factor q determines the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The noise component in the in-ear microphone $V_i(k, l)$ was scaled by the same factor q as $V_o(k, l)$, i.e.,

$$Y_i(k, l) = (S_i(k, l) + U_i(k, l)) + q \cdot V_i(k, l), \quad (15)$$

where $U_i(k, l)$ denotes body-produced noise present during own voice recording. Due to device attenuation, the noise component in the in-ear microphone signal $V_i(k, l)$ has a much lower level than the noise component in the outer microphone signal $V_o(k, l)$, leading to a higher SNR at the in-ear microphone than at the outer microphone. The procedure in (14)-(15) maintains the SNR difference between both microphones. During training, uniformly distributed SNRs between -10 dB and 25 dB were considered at the outer microphone.

Own voice signals and environmental noise signals of the same talker were added, so that they were individually matched. As loss function, the combined L_1 loss in

Table 3 Number of parameters and MACs per second for each layer in the DNN architecture used in the OVR system

Layer	Parameters	MACs/s
F-LSTM	1.06 M	17.14 G
T-LSTM	0.33 M	5.31 G
Dense	516	32 508
Total	1.39 M	22.45 G

M indicates millions, *G* indicates billions

⁴ Related work in [45] investigates low-complexity versions of the OVR system using speech-dependent data augmentation proposed in this paper. Results showed that good performance could still be obtained by a system with only 31 k parameters and a complexity of 0.5 G MACs per second.

time domain and STFT domain (after re-analysis) [46] between the STFT magnitudes was used, i.e.,

$$L = \sum_n |s_o[n] - \hat{s}_o[n]| + \sum_{k,l} \left| |\text{STFT}\{s_o[n]\}(k,l)| - |\text{STFT}\{\hat{s}_o[n]\}(k,l)| \right|, \quad (16)$$

where $s_o[n]$ and $\hat{s}_o[n]$ denote the clean and estimated own voice signal at the outer microphone, respectively. The same STFT parameters as in DNN processing were used to compute the STFT term in the loss. During training, mean-variance normalization was applied to the noisy microphone signals independently for each microphone. As in [47], the mean and variance of the noisy outer microphone signals was also used to scale the corresponding clean own voice components, which serve as the training targets. Each training batch consisted of four utterances. In addition to training with augmented own voice signals, we also investigate additional fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals afterwards. Here, we refer to fine-tuning as further training (selected layers of) a previously trained DNN with a smaller learning rate. We investigate fine-tuning of the dense layer, the T-LSTM layer, the F-LSTM layer, or all layers of the FT-JNF architecture.

For all training procedures, we used the ADAM optimizer [48]; for training with recorded and augmented own voice signals an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} was used, whereas for fine-tuning a smaller initial learning rate of 10^{-5} was used. Training proceeded up to a maximum of 100 epochs, where one epoch corresponds to iterating over the own voice training set once. The learning rate was halved after three consecutive epochs without validation loss improvement, and early stopping was applied after six consecutive epochs without validation loss improvement. The PyTorch [49] (v1.10) framework was used, and computations were executed on two NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER GPUs.

While for most training conditions the recorded own voice signals of all 12 talkers with 306 utterances each were used in training, in Section 5.3 the influence of the number of talkers and the number of recorded utterances per talker is investigated. In these experiments, the numbers of recorded talkers considered are equal to 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 (keeping the number of utterances fixed to 306), while the numbers of recorded utterances per talker considered are equal to 1, 3, 6, 12, 25, 75, 150, and 306 (keeping the number of utterances fixed to 12).

4.4 Evaluation details

The performance of the OVR systems trained using different procedures was evaluated on mixtures of recorded own voice signals and spatialized environmental noise signals. As mentioned before, the test set consists of

recorded own voice signals (306 utterances) from 4 talkers, which are different from the talkers during training. The performance was evaluated at SNRs of -10 , -5 , 0 , 5 , and 10 dB in the outer microphone signal. As in training, own voice signals and environmental noise signals of the same talker are added, so that they are individually matched. As evaluation metrics, we considered the wide-band perceptual evaluation of speech quality (PESQ) [50] and short-time objective intelligibility (STOI) [51] metrics. These metrics were computed for the estimated own voice signal, using the clean own voice component in the outer microphone signals as the reference.

As baseline OVR algorithm, we consider the extreme bandwidth extension network (EBEN) [14], trained with augmented signals and additional fine-tuning with recorded signals. Different from [14], we only train the generator network in a fully supervised scheme with the same loss function in (16). It should be noted that EBEN only uses the in-ear microphone signal as input.

5 Experimental results

In this section, the results of the experimental evaluation are presented and discussed. Section 5.1 compares the influence of the data augmentation techniques on the OVR performance when training with a large amount of augmented data. The results demonstrate that the proposed speech-dependent individual augmentation yields the best performance, outperforming a system trained using only recorded own voice signals. Section 5.2 investigates the potential performance improvement from fine-tuning different layers of the DNN trained using speech-dependent individual augmentation. Section 5.3 explores the trade-off between recording effort and performance for systems trained using recorded own voice signals and systems trained using augmented own voice signals (with or without fine-tuning), both in terms of number of recorded talkers and number of recorded utterances per talker. Audio examples supporting the experimental results are available online⁵.

5.1 Influence of data augmentation techniques

For different SNRs, Fig. 4 shows the performance in terms of PESQ and STOI for systems trained using speech-independent and speech-dependent data augmentation (individual and talker-averaged), as well as a system trained using random phoneme individual data augmentation and a system trained using only recorded own voice signals. The performance metrics for the unprocessed outer and in-ear microphone signals are

⁵ Audio examples [online]: https://m-ohlenbusch.github.io/own_voice_augmentation_examples/

Fig. 4 OVR performance in terms of PESQ (top) and STOI (bottom) for different SNRs, achieved by systems trained either only with recorded own voice signals directly or with simulated own voice signals, obtained through different data augmentation techniques. Data points are slightly shifted horizontally to improve readability

also shown. Circles indicate average results and error bars indicate standard deviations over the test set examples. It should be noted that all OVR systems considered in this section use the entire training and validation dataset of recorded own voice signals (amounting to approx. 6/1 h), either directly or to generate 115.7 h of augmented data (see Table 2).

It can be observed that the proposed speech-dependent augmentation consistently leads to higher performance than speech-independent augmentation for both individual as well as talker-averaged augmentation, with speech-dependent individual augmentation yielding the highest performance in terms of both metrics. In addition, random phoneme individual augmentation leads to higher performance than speech-independent individual augmentation. This can be explained by the additional variance from augmenting with multiple RTFs per talker and matches previously reported results in [13, 14], where an increase in the number of RTFs or introducing additional variance in augmentation improved performance. When comparing random phoneme individual augmentation with speech-dependent individual augmentation, it can be observed that using phoneme-matched RTF selection instead of random RTF selection leads to better results in terms of PESQ and similar results in terms of STOI. This indicates that speech-dependent modeling yields a benefit in addition to the performance gained by augmenting with multiple RTFs per talker. Moreover, the results show that both random phoneme as well as speech-dependent individual data augmentation outperform a system trained on recorded own voice signals (except in terms of STOI at high SNR).

In summary, training an OVR system using speech-dependent individual augmentation technique to simulate a large amount of own voice signals yields the best performance among all considered data augmentation techniques. In the following sections, we will therefore only consider speech-dependent individual augmentation as data augmentation technique.

5.2 Influence of fine-tuning

This section investigates the potential performance improvement by fine-tuning different layers of the DNN architecture (see Fig. 3) with recorded own voice signals after training the OVR system using speech-dependent individual augmentation. Similarly as in the previous section, the entire training and validation dataset of recorded own voice signals (amounting to approx. 6/1 h) is used to generate 115.7 h of augmented data, as well as for fine-tuning. For different SNRs, Fig. 5 shows the PESQ and STOI improvement compared to the noisy outer microphone signal obtained by training only with recorded own voice signals, training only with augmented

Fig. 5 PESQ (top) and STOI (bottom) improvement for different SNRs, achieved by the OVR system trained only with recorded own voice signals, trained only with augmented own voice signals, or by performing additional fine-tuning of different layers with recorded own voice signals. Data points are slightly shifted horizontally to improve readability

own voice signals (without fine-tuning), or performing additional fine-tuning of different layers (dense layer, T-LSTM layer, F-LSTM layer, all layers).

All fine-tuning approaches lead to higher or equal performance than training only with augmented own voice

signals, and significantly better results than training only with recorded signals. While hardly any improvement is obtained by fine-tuning only the dense layer, larger improvements are obtained by fine-tuning only the T-LSTM layer or the F-LSTM layer, and the largest improvements are obtained by fine-tuning all layers.

In summary, the results show that fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals is beneficial in addition to augmented training using transfer characteristic models obtained from the recorded own voice signals. In the following section, only fine-tuning of the full DNN is further considered.

5.3 Influence of amount of recorded own voice signals

In Sections 5.1 and 5.2 the entire training dataset of recorded own voice signals (i.e., 12 talkers, 306 utterances, see Section 4.1) was used for estimating own voice transfer characteristic models as well as for fine-tuning. In this section, the trade-off between OVR performance and the amount of recorded own voice signals used is investigated, both in terms of number of talkers and number of utterances per talker. Three training conditions are compared: training only with recorded own voice signals, training only with augmented own voice signals using speech-dependent individual augmentation, and performing additional fine-tuning (all layers) with recorded own voice signals. It should be noted that irrespective of the assumed amount of recorded own voice signals, 115.7 h of augmented own voice signals are generated. In addition, we also compare to EBEN as a baseline algorithm.

For the considered training conditions, Fig. 6 shows the PESQ and STOI improvement compared to the noisy outer microphone signal for different number of talkers (306 utterances per talker) and different number of utterances per talker (12 talkers). Circles indicate average results and error bars indicate standard deviations over the test set examples and SNRs. For all considered number of talkers and number of utterances per talker, fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals clearly leads to higher performance compared to training only with augmented own voice signals and training only with recorded own voice signals. Training only with augmented own voice signals leads to higher performance than training only with recorded own voice signals (except for Δ PESQ with number of talkers = 1). Moreover, all proposed OVR systems using both microphone signals as input clearly outperform the EBEN baseline algorithm using only the in-ear microphone signal as input.

Investigating the influence of the number of recorded talkers, it can be observed that the performance for all three training conditions generally decreases when the number of talkers is reduced. When training only with

augmented own voice signals, the PESQ scores drop when there are fewer than 4 talkers. When performing additional fine-tuning, the PESQ scores already drop when there are fewer than 8 talkers. While the improvements achieved by fine-tuning over only augmented training are larger for more talkers, the improvements achieved by augmented training over training with recorded own voice signals are larger for fewer talkers (except for a single talker). These results suggest that the proposed speech-dependent individual data augmentation technique is particularly effective when recorded own voice signals of few talkers are available, and additional fine-tuning is more effective when recorded own voice signals of more talkers are available.

Investigating the influence of the number of utterances per talker, it can be observed that the performance for all three training conditions generally decreases when the number of utterances is reduced. When training with recorded own voice signals, the performance strongly decreases, whereas when training with augmented own voice signals, the performance only slightly decreases. When fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals, there is only a small benefit over only augmented training when few utterances per talker are available, but a larger benefit when more utterances per talker are available. The results show that augmented training achieves the largest benefit compared to training with recorded own voice signals when few utterances per talker are available. Since the performance for few utterances is still relatively high, it appears that recording more utterances per talker is less beneficial than recording more talkers for the proposed augmentation technique.

In summary, the results show that the proposed speech-dependent individual augmentation technique enables training an OVR system even when few recorded own voice signals are available. Increasing the recording effort can substantially improve performance, especially by increasing the number of recorded talkers.

6 Discussion

The experiments presented in Section 5 evaluated speech-dependent own voice data augmentation, fine-tuning with recorded signals, and the impact of the amount of recorded signals used for training an own voice reconstruction system.

The results demonstrate significant performance gains when using speech-dependent compared to speech-independent augmentation. A comparison with the random phoneme augmentation technique reveals that about two-thirds of the PESQ improvement can be attributed to introducing random variance to the training data, while the remaining improvement is due to modeling of speech-dependent behavior. In terms of

Fig. 6 PESQ and STOI improvement achieved by the OVR system trained with a different number of recorded talkers (a), (c), and a different number of recorded utterances per talker (b), (d). Three training conditions are considered: training only with recorded own voice signals, training only with augmented own voice signals, and performing additional fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals. The performance of EBEN is also included for comparison. Results were averaged over SNRs of -10 , -5 , 0 , 5 , and 10 dB

STOI, the relative benefit of speech-dependent modeling is smaller, which may be due to differences in how PESQ and STOI measure the difference between processed signals and clean reference signals. Additionally,

comparing speech-dependent individual augmentation to speech-dependent talker-averaged augmentation shows a clear advantage for individual modeling. Interestingly, this contrasts with the finding from [16], where

talker-averaged models performed better in predicting in-ear signals of unseen talkers. This suggests that, in the context of data augmentation for training an OVR system, introducing variance by considering 12 individual RTFs may be more beneficial than achieving a low prediction error.

Fine-tuning experiments revealed that fine-tuning the F-LSTM layer led to larger performance improvements than fine-tuning the T-LSTM layer. One possible explanation is that frequency information may be more relevant for OVR performance than time information. Alternatively it may indicate that the proposed speech-dependent augmentation better captures temporal dynamics than spectral characteristics, leaving more room for improvement in the frequency domain. Another explanation could be the larger number of parameters in the F-LSTM layer than in the T-LSTM layer (see Table 3), which offers more flexibility during fine-tuning.

Training an OVR system only on recorded own voice signals showed limited performance, likely due to the relatively small size of the dataset. This highlights a key advantage of the proposed speech-dependent augmentation technique, which enables training an OVR system when few recorded own voice signals are available. For OVR systems with fewer trainable parameters, a smaller amount of recorded signals may even be sufficient, as investigated in [45].

6.1 Limitations and directions for further research

While this paper addresses several key aspects of speech-dependent own voice data augmentation for training an OVR system, several limitations remain that may be addressed in future work. First, the experiments were conducted using a relatively limited dataset of recorded own voice signals. Experiments with a larger dataset (including more talkers and utterances, such as the Vibravox dataset [32]) could help determine the amount of recorded own voice signals required to outperform augmentation-based training. Second, our evaluation relies exclusively on objective metrics (PESQ and STOI). Given that the perceived quality of band-limited in-ear own voice signals is hard to predict with standard metrics [52], future work should therefore incorporate subjective listening tests to assess quality improvements more comprehensively. Finally, the current OVR systems are trained as generic systems, aiming to reconstruct own voice of many talkers. It is likely that further performance improvements can be achieved through personalization, e.g., similar to the approach in [53] for personalized speech enhancement.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have investigated speech-dependent data augmentation techniques for simulating in-ear own voice signals to train an OVR system. Based on a model of own voice transfer characteristics, a large amount of in-ear own voice signals can be simulated from only a limited amount of recorded own voice signals. Experimental results show that speech-dependent individual augmentation yields higher performance than speech-independent and talker-averaged augmentation and outperforms a system directly trained with the recorded own voice signals. Moreover, additional fine-tuning with recorded own voice signals after training with augmented own voice signals, significantly improves performance. When investigating the required amount of recorded own voice signals, it was found that the number of recorded utterances per talker has a smaller influence than the number of recorded talkers. The results show that the proposed speech-dependent individual data augmentation technique for training an OVR system outperforms the EBEN baseline algorithm and is still highly effective even when a limited amount of recorded own voice signals is available.

Abbreviations

OVR	Own voice reconstruction
DNN	Deep neural network
RTF	Relative transfer function
FT-JNF	Frequency and time joint nonlinear filter
STFT	Short-time Fourier transform
WOLA	Weighted overlap-add
LSTM	Long short-term memory
MACs	Multiply-accumulate operations
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
PESQ	Perceptual evaluation of speech quality
STOI	Short-time objective intelligibility
EBEN	Extreme bandwidth extension network

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Author contribution

MO developed the algorithms, performed the simulations, analyzed the results, and drafted the article. CR and SD critically discussed the developed algorithms and the simulation results with MO and proofread and revised the article. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets used in the current study are available in the Zenodo repositories <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844599> (recorded own voice signals) and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11196867> (individual transfer functions for simulating spatialized environmental noise). The Common Voice speech dataset used in the current study is available at <https://commonvoice.mozilla.org>.

[org/en/datasets](https://github.com/microsoft/DNS-Challenge), the fifth DNS challenge noise dataset is available through the Github repository <https://github.com/microsoft/DNS-Challenge>. The Python code for the DNN architectures are available in the Github repositories <https://github.com/sp-uhh/deep-non-linear-filter> (FT-JNF) and <https://github.com/jhauret/eben> (EBEN). Audio examples are available at https://m-ohlenbusch.github.io/own_voice_augmentation_examples/.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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